

Cobalt(II) Complexes of 5(3)-Methyl pyrazole-3(5)-Carboxamide

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The coordination behaviour of 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxamide (MPA) has been reported by the isolation and characterisation of bis-complexes of Co(II), viz., $\text{Co}(\text{MPA})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{ClO}_4, \text{NO}_3, \text{BF}_4, \text{SCN}, \frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$; $n = 0, 2$). The complexes possess a distorted octahedral structure as revealed from magnetic and electronic (diffuse reflectance and solution) spectral data. The ir data characterise the ligand as a neutral bidentate one coordinating through the amide oxygen and pyrazole-ring nitrogen (tertiary). The counter ion is preferentially coordinated in the solid state but is released in aqueous solution.

BIOCHEMICAL importance of heterocyclic acid amides and their derivatives is well documented¹.

The acid amide group itself is known to play a significant role in many biological processes. On the other hand, metal binding properties of acid amides are of special relevance to the chemistry of proteins which contain a number of amide linkages in their structures. Transition metal complexes of the amides of pyridine carboxylic acids have been studied². As a part of our programme³ of investigation of the coordination behaviour of pyrazole-based ligands, the present communication reports the isolation and physico-chemical characterisation of bis-complexes of cobalt(II) with 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxamide (I, herein-after abbreviated as MPA) which might have potential biological significance.

Experimental

(A) Preparation of the ligand :

The ligand, 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxamide (MPA), was prepared by the reaction of liquor ammonia with an ethanolic solution of ethyl 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylate^{3b}. The product on recrystallisation from ethanol melts at 174° (lit⁴ m.p. 174°).

(B) Preparation of the Co(II) complexes :

(i) $\text{Co}(\text{MPA})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}/\text{Br}/\text{I}/\text{ClO}_4/\text{NO}_3/\text{BF}_4/\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$) : A solution of the hydrated cobalt(II) salt, $\text{CoX}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mole) in ethanol (aqueous

ethanol in case of nitrate and fluoborate ; water in case of sulphate) was mixed with a solution of the ligand (0.02 mole) in the same solvent. The resulting reddish-pink solution was concentrated at water-bath temperature to a small volume and then cooled to room temperature when a pink compound with varying shades separated out. The compound, in each case, was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol (with water also for the sulphate complexes) and dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

(ii) $\text{Co}(\text{MPA})_2(\text{SCN})_2$: Ethanolic solutions of the hydrated cobalt(II) nitrate, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (0.01 mole) and potassium thiocyanate (0.02 mole) were mixed together and the precipitated KNO_3 was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to a small bulk and then filtered directly into an ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mole). The resulting solution, after heating at water-bath temperature for 10 min, was cooled to room temperature ; the precipitated light pink compound was collected and dried as before.

(C) Elemental analyses and physico-chemical measurements :

Cobalt content of the complexes was estimated gravimetrically as anhydrous CoSO_4 except the perchlorate complex where the metal was estimated gravimetrically as cobalt mercurithiocyanate after decomposing the complex with conc. HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 mixture. Halogen was estimated as silver halide while sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 in the usual manner. Nitrogen was determined micro-analytically. The equivalent conductances, magnetic susceptibilities, electronic spectra (drs and solution) and ir spectra for the complexes were recorded as described earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analyses of the complexes along with their colours and effective

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	%Co		%N		% Anion(X)		μ_{eff} in B.M. (298°K)
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
Co(MPA) ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	pink	14.16	14.20	20.19	20.30	17.04	16.88	4.52
Co(MPA) ₂ Br ₂ ·2H ₂ O	pink	11.66	11.58	16.64	16.61	31.64	31.51	5.15
Co(MPA) ₂ I ₂ ·2H ₂ O	brown	9.83	9.97	14.03	13.97	42.37	42.21	5.20
Co(MPA) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	reddish pink	10.82	10.80	15.44	15.32	13.03***	13.33	4.83
Co(MPA) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	violet	12.56	12.41	23.88*	23.75	—	—	4.62
Co(MPA) ₂ (BF ₄) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	pink	11.36	11.50	16.20	16.11	—	—	4.84
Co(MPA) ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	pink	13.35	13.42	19.04	19.20	21.77	21.62	5.02
Co(MPA) ₂ (SCN) ₂	light pink	13.85	13.76	26.34**	26.21	15.04****	15.12	4.88

* Including nitrogen present in nitrate ;

** Including nitrogen present in thiocyanate ;

*** Percentage of chlorine ;

**** Percentage of sulphur.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	State	Absorption: maxima in kK (ϵ_{max})	ν_2 (Calcd.)	Dq	B	β
Co(MPA) ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	8.2 ; 16.2 ; 19.5 19.2(21.6)	17.5	932	828	0.85
Co(MPA) ₂ Br ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	9.6 ; 15.0 ; 17.4sh ; 20.2 17.2(27.9) ; 18.7(28.2)	20.3	1079	786	0.81
Co(MPA) ₂ I ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	9.4 ; 13.6 ; 16.8sh ; 20.5 16.9(31.4) ; 18.9(30.9) ; 25.0(101.5)	20.2	1080	807	0.83
Co(MPA) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	9.0 ; 13.3sh ; 20.0 16.9(28.0) ; 18.5(24.5)	19.2	1017	811	0.84
Co(MPA) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	9.0 ; 17.2 ; 18.8 16.9(62.3) ; 18.0(49.6) ; 21.0sh(20.0)	19.0	1002	801	0.82
Co(MPA) ₂ (BF ₄) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	8.8 ; 19.0sh ; 20.0 19.6(16.4)	18.8	996	824	0.85
Co(MPA) ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	8.4 ; 15.8sh ; 19.4 19.2(29.9)	17.9	952	808	0.83
Co(MPA) ₂ (SCN) ₂	Reflectance Methanol	8.6 ; 15.8sh ; 19.0 ; 20.0sh 16.1sh(11.4) ; 19.2(46.2)	18.4	976	770	0.75

magnetic moment values are given in Table 1. The complexes are fairly soluble in water and low-molecular weight alcohols. Molar conductance values of aqueous solutions of the complexes lying in the range 230-290 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ indicate their ionic nature atleast in the aqueous solution. The room temperature magnetic moment values of all the present cobalt(II) complexes, except the chloride and the nitrate, fall within the range 4.8-5.2 B.M. expected for six-coordinate high-spin cobalt(II) complexes⁶. The low magnetic moment values for the chloride (4.52 B.M.) and the nitrate (4.62 B.M.) complexes suggest that they may have an orbital singlet ground state with a distorted octahedral environment⁷.

The diffuse reflectance spectral data of the complexes with respective ligand field parameters are given in Table 2. The spectra, in general, consist of two main broad bands, one appearing in the region 9.6-8.2 kK and the other in 20.5-18.8 kK which may be recognised as $\nu_1[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)]$ and $\nu_2[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)]$ transitions in an average

octahedral field⁸. The values of ligand-field parameters Dq, B and β (Table 2) calculated from the assigned band positions of ν_1 and ν_2 (in an idealised O_h symmetry) by means of known relations⁹, suggest an average octahedral environment of Co(II) ion in these complexes⁸. The calculated ν_2 band positions obtained from the relationship $\nu_2 = \nu_1 + 10 Dq$, are found to appear, in most cases, much close to the observed ν_2 bands; a close scrutiny reveals that the ν_2 transitions remain practically unobserved in the spectra of most of the present Co(II) complexes [except in the spectrum of Co(MPA)₂(BF₄)₂·2H₂O] where the weak shoulder at ~19.0 kK may be taken as ν_2 , as is also expected¹⁰ from the weak nature and proximity of the $\nu_2[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)]$ transition to a strong ν_3 band. Therefore, it is suggestive that the weak bands often appearing as shoulder on the low energy side of the ν_3 band might be due to the presence of low symmetry components in the ligand field. The broad asymmetric nature of the ν_1 band indicating superimposition of the different

components into a single one also supports the above proposition.

The electronic spectral data of the methanolic solution (pink) of the complexes indicate that there is no significant change in the stereochemistry of the complexes on dissolution. The spectra, in general, consists of a characteristic octahedral Co(II) band appearing in the region 19.6-18.5 kK which can be recognised as the ν_s transition in O_h symmetry; appearance of this band at lower wave number compared to the solid suggests some degree of solvation¹⁰. Low values of molar extinction coefficients give additional support for the pseudo-octahedral environment in most of the complexes. The high ϵ values (50-60) observed for the nitrate and thiocyanate complexes may be due to a distortion from octahedral structure⁹. The high intensity band of $\text{Co(MPA)}_2\text{I}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methanol at ~ 25.0 kK ($\epsilon=101$) might be of charge transfer origin.

IR spectra: The ir spectral data of the present complexes when compared with the free ligand give positive indications of the donor atoms of the ligand molecule to the Co(II) ion. The most important ir bands of the free ligand appearing at 3360, 1670, 1570, 1420 and 670 cm^{-1} may be assigned to NH stretching vibration (hydrogen bonded), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the pyrazole ring, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ of the amide group and in-plane deformation of the pyrazole ring, respectively.

The most remarkable change that occurs in the ir spectra of the metal complexes as compared to the uncomplexed ligand is the negative shift of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ by $\sim 10-20$ cm^{-1} and a positive shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ (of the amide group) by $\sim 10-30$ cm^{-1} . These data strongly point to the participation^{9,11} of the amide oxygen atom in complexation since coordination through the amide oxygen atom would tend to increase the single bond character of the carbonyl group and the double bond character of the C-N group thereby decreasing the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and increasing the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$, respectively. A comparatively smaller negative shift of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ than those usually observed in reported amide metal complexes may be ascribed to some sort of hydrogen bonding effect².

Appreciable positive shifts of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (by $\sim 10-15$ cm^{-1}) and the in-plane deformation (by $\sim 10-30$ cm^{-1}) of the pyrazole ring in the complexes compared to the free ligand suggest the tertiary ring nitrogen atom as a possible bonding site. This conclusion is in good agreement with the earlier observations^{1,2} on the metal complexes of N-heterocycles and is also in conformity with the crystallographic studies of several pyrazole metal complexes¹².

The bands in the 3μ region are a bit complicated in the ir spectra of the complexes due to the presence of $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ bands arising out of the presence of water molecules in the species and no useful conclusion can be drawn. The sharp bands at $\sim 970-990$ cm^{-1} in the fluoborate and

sulphate complexes could be recognised as the rocking mode of coordinated water molecules¹⁴.

The mode of linkage of the counterion, viz., thiocyanate, nitrate, perchlorate, fluoborate and sulphate, has been inferred from the ir spectra of the metal complexes. The strong bands at 2100 and 780 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{Co(MPA)}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ may respectively be attributed to the $\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ vibration of an N-bonded NCS group¹⁰. Coordination¹⁵ of the nitrate ion to the metal in $\text{Co(MPA)}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is established by the appearance of bands characteristics of a monodentate nitrate ion in C_{2v} symmetry, viz., the split components of ν_s at 1370(s) and 1310 cm^{-1} (m) and ν_a at 820 cm^{-1} (s). In the spectrum of $\text{Co(MPA)}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the ir band of the perchlorate group due to Cl-O stretching frequency is split into three components appearing at 1140(m), 1110(m) and 1080(s) cm^{-1} ; the extent of splitting indicate the presence of coordinated perchlorate group¹⁶. Appearance of strong broad band covering the region 1100-1020 cm^{-1} and 1150-1050 cm^{-1} in the spectra of fluoborate and sulphate complex respectively indicate that fluoborate¹⁷ and sulphate¹⁸ ions retain their ionic character in the present Co(II) complexes. It appears, therefore, that the ligand 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxamide acts as a neutral bidentate ligand coordinating to the Co(II) ion through the pyrazole ring nitrogen (tertiary) and the amide oxygen in forming distorted octahedral Co(II) species, $\text{Co(MPA)}_2\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($n=0, 2$), where the anionic counterpart is preferentially coordinated.

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